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Moral Issues in Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) Facilitating Learning in the Church

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Abstract

One issue that has generated much debate and discussion in recent time globally is the issue of Artificial Intelligence (AI). This paper is an effort at contributing to the discussion with the aim of educating those using AI or desiring to use it on the moral issues involve in its use to facilitate learning in the church. The premise of this paper is that there are moral issues in AI-system that facilitators of learning and learners need to know in order to appreciate AI and to better appropriate it in the teaching ministry of the Church This paper highlight the moral issues and proffer possible responses that will ensure better understanding of AI -system. Recommendations are given on AI- system facilitated learning. The paper is quasi-empirical; it is theoretical in nature. The method adopted for the work is the historical-survey that permits exploration of relevant materials such as text, oral information, video clip, picture, etc that are relevant to the work. The work location is Lagos State, which is one of the thirty-six states in Nigeria.

Keywords: Moral Issue, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Learning, Church

Introduction

Learning is the key to understanding and knowledge acquisition. No individual grows in knowledge and experience gathering without learning. Similarly, learning is central to family and societal progress. Thus, learning is essential to individual and society healthy living. C. B. Eavey describes learning as acquisition of knowledge through various ways and applying them to daily life (Eavey, 1940). John M. Gregory in his own contribution described learning as gathering of experience. The experience according to him may consist of facts, truths, doctrines, ideas, or ideals. It may further consist of the processes of acquiring skills (Gregory, 2006). Thus, one may conclude that learning is knowledge and skill acquisition by individual and group. Learning is obtained through formal, informal, and non-formal. Two ideas prominent in the word learning or education that give meaning of the word are: Leading out into new knowledge and experience, feeding to cause growth and development. Learning is a process, not a product. It is a change in knowledge, belief, behaviour, or attitude. Learning is individually done and cannot be done for the learner.

Formal learning takes place in specially built institutions such as mission or church schools and colleges. What is taught is carefully structured by means of syllabi and time-tables; the teaching provided is usually carefully supervised by an appointed body. The achievement of those who learn in formal education is often recognised by the award of certificate (Farrant, 1980).

Non-Formal Learning is organised learning activity outside the structure of the formal learning system that is consciously aimed at meeting specific learning needs of particular group such as children, youth, adult, etc in the church or community or both. Learning activities engage in at this level may include: skill training, piggery, fishing, dyeing, health & family planning, etc. What is learned is structured but not as strong as the formal; and is flexible on method to use e.g. AI, traditional teaching, self-teaching, etc. It is also flexible regarding centre or place of learning (Farrant, 1980). Non-formal learning takes place through correspondence schools, and technology driven centre of learning. Informal learning does not involve structuring, learning occurs unconsciously, like things a child learns from his family, friends, experience and environment

The conceptual framework of this study is determining the relationship between AI-system and Learning facilitation in the church. The question then arises how do a Christian teacher makes learning effective in the church using AI technology or the traditional method of facilitating learning or both. This work focus is on

AI and learning in the context of the church. The work agreed that AI can be used to teach the Holy Bible and Christian literatures to all category of age grade in the church. It however, warns of the ethical issues in the use of AI to facilitate learning in the church. Thus, the paper advises its readers to give consideration to the ethical issues so as not to adversely impact the church

The theoretical framework adopted for this work is the Behavioural theory postulated by John B. Watson in association with Ivan Pavlov. Behavioural theory says that learning through resources available in the society or environment to which the learner has contact or interaction with can influence his/her behaviour positively or negatively or both. The theory says further that innate or inherited factors have very little influence on behaviour. Therefore, AI-system facilitated learning as well as human facilitated learning have the potential to influence learner behaviour in every context they are used whether secular or religion context. Therefore, the church must be careful and cautious concerning the mechanism she proposed or resolved to use in facilitating learning ('What Is The Behavioral Learning Theory?', 2020).

Ways of Making Learning Effective

Effective as used means learning that is fruitful and result-oriented. It means learning that causes positive change to occur in the life of the learner. Therefore, learning can be made effective through the following ways:

1. Learning must interact with the original nature, environment and the purpose of each learner because they constitute learning factors.
2. Learning must include mental activity without it, learners cannot develop mentally and psychologically.
3. Learning must include clues to solving learner's life problems and also meeting their felt needs.
4. Learning must touch learners in three areas of their lives. These are to know, to feel, and to do.
5. Learning must evolve from a clear understanding of the subject to be facilitated, educational principles, and educational methods.
6. Learning must be evolved from adequate academic and spiritual preparation that is subsumed under the leadership of the Holy Spirit.
7. Learning must be evolved from a deep understanding of the means of control by which the learning of the learner is started, directed, changed or stopped.
8. Learning must emphasize character more than content. Character learning focuses on the heart, which consists of mind, emotion, and conduct.
9. Learning must be transmitted in word, deed, example, symbol and sign.
10. Learning should promote intimacy and cordial relationship that transcend master-servant relationship.
11. Learning should focus on bringing out the best in learners not the worst.
12. Learning must be evolved from willingness, commitment, hard work, faith, trust, and believe in its success.
13. Learning must be dynamic and not static and should emphasize individual/group learning more than crowd learning.
14. Learning must be interactive and must be transmitted in an atmosphere of freedom, love, courage and friendship.
15. Learning should be facilitated through several methods such as differentiated instruction, lecture-based instruction, technology-based learning, group learning, individual learning, inquiry-based learning, kinesthetics learning and expeditionary learning.
16. Teaching method that is best for each context or teaching assignment should be used.

17. Every teacher needs to put effort at knowing various teaching methods and try to improve him/herself by testing the various teaching methods in his/her teachings using the same lesson; and through interaction with fellow teachers.

Concept of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence is a branch of computer science that seeks to develop computer systems that replicate or mimic cognitive tasks ascribed to human such as teaching, voice recognition, Language processing, etc (Hamlen, 2017). AI has improved human ability to use computer, facilitate repetitious tasks human find difficult to do or inaccurate or slow doing the task; assist human with disabilities; AI is assisting medical personnel in providing care to the sick and it has led to production of Smartphones that accept voice command.

AI was conceived by Alan Turing who suggested that if a machine's behaviour is indistinguishable from human, it can be considered 'intelligent' for practical purpose (Hamlen, 2017). AI has successfully been deployed in commerce, mathematics of probability, statistics, logic, etc (Hamlen, 2017). AI is a rapidly developing technology that involves the creation of intelligent machines that perform tasks typically requiring human intelligence such as learning, problem-solving, and decision-making. AI is widely used to monitor research of different types of cases and to also analyse past research outcome.

Some ways of Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) to Facilitates Learning

The possibility of using AI facilitated learning in Churches in Nigeria is high and realizable in this contemporary time. However, many churches in Nigeria have not started using AI facilitated learning perhaps due to inadequate fund to kick-start it; ignorance of it use and benefit; high cost of data/energy to power and make it functional; and phobia or biase concerning it use in the church. AI can be used to create smarter class that enhance learning experience of learner; it can be used to collect and analyse student data on interaction with learning material, assignment completion time, administer test and examined overall student performance in order to understand each student attitude and need

AI enhances language learning in the area of word pronunciation, grammar construction and vocabulary repertoire or banking. AI uses Chatbots and virtual tutors to provide swift assistance and foster self-directed learning. AI chatbots are re-shaping student learning experience. Chatbot (chatterbot) is a computer program that simulates human conversation through voice commands or textchats or both. AI facilitated learning has the following features that distinguish it from the traditional learning method. It is student centred; it is highly personalized; automated grading and instant feedback regarding learner; extensive online resource and content; adaptive to individual pace; enhanced engagement through interactivity; advanced data analysis for insight; remote and flexible learning options; high cost of execution and globally scalable ('AI learning'). These aforementioned features of AI corroborated the submissions of others who have submitted that AI technology is applicable to learning facilitation in both secular and religious institutions globally. In spite, of the benefits enunciated there are moral issues that cannot be ignored in the usage of AI to facilitate learning in church and society.

Moral Issues in AI facilitated Learning

There is need to explain succinctly what constitute moral and moral issue before enumerating the moral issues contained in in AI facilitated learning. The explanation is needful to help readers understand and appreciate the issue discussed in the paper. Moral as a word refers to good and praiseworthy character and action; it means something just, honourable and ideal. Morality which is formed from the word moral is derived from the Latin word 'Mos or More' meaning custom or habitual habit. It is the distinction between right and wrong in relation to action, conduct and character or that which is concerned with virtue and vice

(Asha, 2019). In essence morality has to do with the assessment of human actions, inactions and expressions for the purpose of determining their rightness and wrongness as well as their goodness and badness (Asha, 2019). Thus, morality implies human responsibility in interpersonal relationship at formal and informal levels.

It is only among human beings that moral discussion is meaningful and importance because human beings are created in God's image. Moral Knowledge and moral action are essential for the peace, progress, and success of human society, as well as human institution like the Prison service, Nigeria. The moral law of nature is found in the Greek cardinal virtues which are wisdom, temperance, fortitude and justice ((Asha, 2022).

Moral issues on the other hand are issues having to do with morality. Any action or decision that has moral implication on one and other persons is a moral issue. Moral issues are classified into positive and negative (Ayantayo, 2011). Positive indicates what should be done or embraced or the attitude to cultivate; while negative indicates prohibition, issue to be avoided or done away with or to be condemned in relationship to AI facilitated learning.

Moral issue has to do with the issue of right and wrong in human relationship as it relates to God and fellow human. Moral issue has to do with what is right and wrong in human action, decision, and saying in their relationship with God and fellow human. Before the right can be done and the wrong avoided, they must be known because it may not be humanly possible to do what is right and avoid what is wrong if one does not know what constitute right and wrong things. No wonder it is stated in the Holy Bible that 'you will know the truth and the truth will set you free' (John8:32). Norman Geisler affirms this fact by saying that doing what is right brings the greatest good for the greatest number of persons in the long run (Geisler, 2007). The moral issues emanating from AI facilitated learning in the context of the Christian church; the Christian Church implies the assembly of those who confess Jesus Christ as their Lord, Master, Teacher, and Saviour and have become His followers through Baptism and fellowship with him in the church- a physical structure built for the purpose of fellowship, worship, learning, and service to God and fellow human (Mbewe, 2020). One significant concern regarding AI in religious context revolves around playing God. Sterling Martin Allen argued that the creation of AI systems with human –like intelligence is viewed as an attempt by humans to assume God-Like powers, potentially challenging divine authority and agency (Allen, 2024). This issue raises the questions about human boundaries and human creativity limit in relation to God's sovereignty (Allen, 2024). God hates rivalry and does not want his creatures especially human to compete with his sovereignty power. He has set limit to human creative ability which he does not want human being to ignore or go beyond. There is usually consequence for any of God's creature who goes beyond God's limit. Satan, an angelic being is one example (Rev12:7-9); the people in the tower of Babel story is another example (Genesis 11:1-9). These mentioned people went beyond their given boundaries or limits and they were duly punished for doing so.

The issue of decision making regarding learning content and learner is another issue of concern. The Christian resolved is that every decision concerning church work must be subjected to Holy Spirit leading without which such work or action will not be reckoned with and acceptable to the church. AI systems possess the ability to process vast amounts of data and to make decisions based on algorithms and patterns without recourse to the Holy Spirit. AI facilitated action/decision may also not align with the evangelical Christian Church doctrinal belief on Holy Spirit. Therefore, the use of AI to facilitate learning in the church requires thorough appraisal and examination in order not to adversely affect the church and her faith which Jesus bought and redeemed with his life –body and blood. This view was shared by Samuel Adetule, a Christian and expert in Information Technology and AI University of Lagos.

The integration of AI as instrument of teaching in the church may ignite conflicts between the principles encoded within the AI systems and the basic beliefs (orthodoxy) and practices (orthopraxy) of the Christian

church. In addition, over reliance on AI system to teach and to do other church work may impact negatively on human dignity, value and usefulness in God's vineyard. Moreover, it will adversely affect human ability to socialise and relate with fellow believer in the church and community where every Christian is expected to be light and encourager to people (Allen, 2024).

The use of AI-powered chatbots for teaching and counselling may raise concern about the authenticity and meaningfulness of the teaching-counselling experience. Because a facilitator of learning specifically human is expected to provide empathy, spiritual guidance, and physical presence which AI systems cannot authentically provide. Furthermore, AI technology can enable virtual religious ceremonies and rituals by allowing learners to participate remotely. However, the substitution of physical presence with virtual experiences may raise the issues of authenticity and spiritual significance of such act or ritual. Thus, such should not be promoted above the need for physical presence in church meeting. At best, virtual worship meetings should complement physical church meetings and not to become substitute for physical meeting. The issue of distortion and misinterpretation of basic Christian church learning resources by AI facilitors is high because AI system is capable of collecting several learning resources from different Christian doctrinal sources but may lack the ability to sift and contextualise the facts to fit into each church doctrinal context if caution is not taken distortion of historical beliefs may occur as well as misinterpretation, confusion and heresy.

The issue of bias and unfairness cannot be rule out in AI systems when use to facilitate learning in the church; because it is human being that design and develop the system; if the designer and developer is a racist or tribalist and a xenophobic person, it is certain that his/her bias may be infused into the system. And when that happened it will manifest when the system is used to facilitate learning. The resultant effect on the learners who may come from different ethnic or racial background will be animosity, ill-feeling against another ethnic group, hatred, division, uninformed criticism and unhealthy opposition of fellow group learner (Bossman, 2016).

The use of AI-system to facilitate learning in the church may render ministers called and trained for the teaching ministry of the church redundant and under-utilised. Invariably it may render trained minister redundant, jobless and without call to pastorate (Bossman, 2016). Presently there are several trained ministers who are yet to receive call to pastorate for several reasons of which AI may be one of them. The idea of multi-staff pastoral ministry that is been promoted and encouraged as one of the solutions to unemployment or lack of call to pastorate may be threatened if not already been threatened by AI-system. The issue of reward or compensation is another issue raised regarding the use of AI in facilitating learning in church; how will the successes and failures be apportioned among the stakeholders such as AI machine tool and human being called to church ministry, human leader in the church, the triune God who owns the Church, and the machine designer or developer. How will success and failure be share to ensure equity and fairness among stakeholders involve in facilitating learning in the church

Conclusion

This work discussed learning as one of the essential reasons for why the Christian church exists; and learning cannot take place without teaching, thus teaching is germane to church growth and development; teaching and discipleship making are included in the Great Commission God gave to the church through Jesus Christ. Every ideal Church knows the importance of learning by calling trained minister to handle her teaching ministry. It is also true to say that AI-system technology is developed by human scientist globally to assist human and human organisation do their work correctly, efficiently and speedily in all strand of human exploration such as social, economic, education, medical, transport, military, science, religion, etc. Hence AI is now a phenomenon in the global workspace that cannot be ignored or toyed with today. This study

highlighted the moral issues involved in using AI system to facilitate teaching-learning process in the church; and conclude with recommendations given below.

Recommendations

AI-system has become a reality and no human institution either secular or religion can feign ignorance. There is need for adequate knowledge and understanding of AI-system by churches in order to know its use in the context of the church through teaching and training on the use of AI;

Every ideal church will need to develop moral guideline to guide her usage of AI system in facilitating learning in the church; place priority on human value and worth than machine design to mimic human function in church and society; and be careful, cautious, patience, in adopting AI systems to teaching in the church. The church should not substitute human learning facilitators with machine learning facilitators such as robots because robot cannot give the ministry of presence needed by every human learner neither can it yield to Holy spirit control every hour and at every duty post. These recommendations if acted upon and given the needed consideration will enhance churches knowledge and appreciation of AI-tools.

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